

Emergence of graphene-based biosensors for improved treatment response prediction in major depressive disorder: a perspective

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Abstract: Major depressive disorder (MDD), a leading cause of disability worldwide, is primarily characterized by symptoms such as loss of interest and depressed mood. Although effective treatment strategies are generally available for MDD, there is a large variability in treatment response between individual patients. Therefore, there is an urgent need to identify reliable and easily accessible predictors to guide treatment decisions. To date, there are no tests that can predict the individual treatment response based on biofluids such as blood, serum, plasma, and saliva. Due to the increasing number of patients suffering from MDD, there is an urgent need for modern techniques such as biosensors to predict the treatment outcome and to potentially identify responsive subgroups for individual treatments. Recent research on various biomarkers for MDD provides an opportunity to develop biosensors to overcome the challenges faced by the conventional diagnostic tools. Over the past decade, considerable efforts have been made to achieve this goal. In this process, graphene and its derivatives have worked as an excellent transducer material for the design of sensitive electrochemical and electrical biosensing platforms. Therefore, the integration of graphene with the potential MDD biomarkers offers a promising approach towards the realization of reliable and cost-effective biosensors. This perspective provides an insight into the recent developments in the electrochemical and electrical biosensors for MDD biomarker quantification designed using graphene and its derivatives. We also discuss the major challenges and next steps required for the development and further optimization of biosensors for monitoring the response to different treatment options in MDD.

Keywords: Major depressive disorder, graphene, biosensor, electrochemical, electrical.

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1. Introduction: Mental health is a growing concern among adults across the globe, and according to the world health organization (WHO), it may become the leading cause of disease burden by 2030 [1]. Although there are more than 1.5 billion annual cases worldwide, it is still a neglected and underestimated public health issue, as the emotional discrepancies are less visible (and with this potentially less acceptable) than physical injuries and other common diseases [2]. Different kinds of mental disorders contribute to more than 14% of the global burden of the disease due to a high rate of mortality and disability[3]. Among them, major depressive disorder (MDD) is the second most common mental illness, has been ranked as the third leading cause of the burden of disease by the WHO [4] and affects > 300 million people worldwide [5]. The prevalence of MDD among European Union (EU) citizens is continuously increasing. For example, in 2019, it was reported to be at 7.2%, which was 0.3% higher as compared to 2014[6] and yet does not take into account potentially further elevated numbers after COVID-19 pandemic [7]. MDD can cause a negative impact on the developmental trajectory of children and adolescents, and with suicide it is the second leading cause of death among 10-19 year-olds [8]. Existing diagnosis includes both non-laboratory and laboratory tests. Non-laboratory methods like self-assessment questionnaires including the 9-item Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), and Centre for Epidemiologic Studies Depression scale (CES-D) [9], which are generally inaccurate as they are subjective to the patient [10]. On the other hand available laboratory techniques like neuroimaging [11], and mass spectrometry test [12], are expensive and require large and high-cost equipment, which does not serve the purpose of having an essay to use, cost-effective and reliable tool for understanding the heterogeneity of the disease and assisting more focused individual treatment of the patients. Considering the level of threat posed by the MDD to our society, it is highly crucial to look for reliable predictors of antidepressant response to assist in treatment decisions early on or even before treatment begins. Although there are number of studies reporting potential clinical, genetic, neurobiological predictors; however, no predictor is still identified having sufficient clinical utility in selecting the specific antidepressants for individual patients [13]. In this regard, availability of biomarkers present in body fluids offers an opportunity to develop tools for monitoring the response of antidepressant treatment methods in depressed individuals [14]. MDD is primarily linked to systematic and central dysfunctions, therefore biomarkers associated with kidney dysfunction, innate immunity, anemia, growth hormone, and testosterone deficiency have been associated [15, 16]. Previously, only a limited number of biomarkers were available including cytokines, hormones, metabolites, and oxidative stress markers [17, 18]. The significant success in the research and development of new classes of promising MDD biomarkers offers a rich option for designing biosensors for their monitoring and by this improving medical support for the patients.

Presently, the detection of MDD primarily relies on the clinical symptoms and the scale rate, without including the application of any kind of analytical device, challenging the detection and evaluation of clinical therapies [16]. Biosensors, which are used for the detection of biomarkers of different disease like cancers and infections such as COVID-19 have the potential to enable the designing of selective, precise, and sensitive tools for MDD monitoring [16]. A biosensor is an analytical device that converts the binding events of biological reactions on the sensing electrode into measurable signals. Typically, a biosensor contains a bioreceptor molecule with a transducer unit, which converts the quantitative signal into a measurable unit, which is directly proportional to the biomarker concentrations. The most common methods are electrochemical and electrical biosensors, for which the choice of transducer plays a key role in achieving improved sensing parameters like sensitivity and limit of detection. Graphene and its derivatives, which belongs to the two-dimensional nanomaterials (2D NM) family are known as a suitable transducers for electrical and electrochemical biosensing applications due to their excellent conductivity [19]. Additional features beneficial to the detection of biomarkers include, (a) high specific surface area (a theoretical surface area of 2630 m²/g, offers high density attachment of the biorecognition molecules, which offers improved detection sensitivity for the biomarkers [20]. (b) The exceptional electrical conductivity of graphene originates from the sp² bonded carbon atoms with π - π conjugate system offering free mobility of electrons [20]. (c) Chemical stability of graphene further ensures the durability of the biosensors. (d) Ease of functionalization offers the possibility of the attachment of a

range of biorecognition elements, which enhances the selectivity and specificity for the biomarker detection. (e) Being one of the strongest known materials, graphene offers possibilities of designing flexible biosensors for MDD biomarker detection. (f) The ultrahigh surface area makes graphene a highly suitable electrode for biosensing in biofluids like blood, and serum. Although there is a possibility of adherence of fouling biomolecules to the graphene surface, abundance of electroactive surface area within the pores, cervices, and protruding edge-planes allows sufficient electron transfer [21]. It is important to note that the observed capability of the graphene-based electrode to offer enhanced electrochemical/electrical properties in complex media is not due to the active antifouling mechanism but rather inherent diminished sensitivity towards the biofouling, which makes graphene a suitable candidate for detection of MDD biomarkers in complex biological media [21].

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of designing graphene-based biosensors for monitoring therapy responses. Different MDD biomarkers such as dopamine, C-reactive protein (CRP), cortisol, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) etc., present in the biological fluids (blood, urine, saliva, interstitial/cerebrospinal fluids) of the patients can be detected using the graphene electrode by immobilizing biorecognition elements such as antibodies, aptamers, peptides, molecularly imprinted polymers (MIP). The specific binding of the MDD biomarkers with the immobilized bioreceptor is realized using the techniques based on electrochemical and field-effect transistors. Advanced point-of-care diagnostics tools, and wearables for monitoring MDD biomarkers can also be fabricated using graphene and its derivatives.

2. Potential biomarkers for MDD: biomarkers for MDD can be defined as the indicators, reflecting the dysfunctions of the central nervous system, other organs, and pathogenic processes or response to stress or physiological conditions [3]. Biomarkers are persistent and suggest the individual's condition before, after and during the process of recovery. Depending on the reliability of the biomarker, a good prediction value reflects the possibility for the person suffering from MDD, while a negative predictive value suggests no depression. This approach also offers the potential to generate a predictive measure

of depression likelihood, aiding in the early-stage monitoring of therapeutic responses for MDD [13]. Considering the wide range of MDD biomarkers, we have classified them into five following categories.

Table 1: Classification of the potential MDD biomarkers, and symptom associated with the patients suffering from MDD.

<i>Biomarker classification</i>	<i>Finding on biomarkers</i>	<i>References</i>
<i>Neuroendocrine</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atypical depression can show hypercortisolism. • Elevated cortisol levels may indicate a reduced effectiveness of psychological and pharmacological therapies. • An overactive HPA axis is commonly observed in individuals with depression. 	[22-24]
<i>Inflammation</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antidepressant treatment has been shown to reduce inflammation over time. • Proinflammatory markers are significantly elevated in individuals with depression compared to controls. • Inflammation appears to be more pronounced in individuals who do not respond to treatment. 	[25-27]
<i>Neurotransmitter</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monoamines interact to affect cognitive function and stress responses, which may help explain the mechanisms behind treatment-resistant depression. • In people with depression, 5-HT_{1A} binding is widely increased and can be influenced by treatment. 	[28] [29]
<i>Growth Factor (GF)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In depression, growth factors like VEGF and bFGF may be produced in excess. • In depression, neurotrophic factors like BDNF, NGF, and GDNF are lower than in healthy individuals. • Neurotrophic factors increase with treatment, even if the patient does not respond to it. 	[23, 24, 30]
<i>Metabolic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The potential of metabolic markers to improve depression treatments is limited by confounding factors such as BMI and severity. • Atypical depression is associated with more significant metabolic abnormalities. • Depression is linked to changes in metabolic profiles. 	[31-33]

HPA: Hypothalamic pituitary adrenal; 5HT: 5-hydroxytryptamine; VEGF: vascular endothelial growth factor; bFEG: basic fibroblast growth factor; BDNF: Brain-derived neurotrophic factor; NGF: nerve growth factor; GDNF: Glial cell-derived neurotrophic factor; BMI: Body mass index.

Based on the previous studies on the pathology of the MDD development, alteration in the concentration of different key species like proteins, enzymes, hormones, and other biomolecules play significant role in the process of MDD development. The corresponding increase or decrease in the concentration of these species present in the body fluids may be utilized as an effective tool to monitor the therapy response of different antidepressant treatment strategies. For example, proteases which are emerging as a promising biomarker for the MDD, particularly extracellular matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) 2/9 has altered level in schizophrenic patients [34]. Cortisol is another important biomarker, a steroid hormone presents in urine, human saliva, and blood, produced by the adrenal cortex [35]. Cortisol helps in activating metabolism, and providing energy to human body, and regulating mental reactions against stress. Concentration of cortisol increases after the mental and physical stress making it suitable biomarker for the MDD. Similarly, there are other molecules shows alteration in their concentrations on the onset of MDD, can serve as potential biomarker for the therapy response evaluation. In the following sections, we have discussed these kinds of species and their potential application in MDD management.

Various studies suggest that due to the inflammatory mechanism of MDD, classical inflammatory markers such as CRP, interleukin, TNF- α , and other cytokines are associated with depression [17, 36]. In the depressed individual, the CRP level is elevated, which is reported to be more pronounced in patients having treatment-resistant depression [37]. Recent studies from the UK biobanks reveal higher blood CRP and interleukin-6 (IL-6) in depressed patients compared to the control group [38]. CRP is an acute phase protein, expressed and released by the liver together with endothelial cells, and immune cells in response to cytokine signalling [39]. Levels of CRP in plasma and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) make a positive correlation with respect to central inflammation, suggesting the possibility of using CRP as a biomarker for therapy-response applications [40]. BDNF is a paracrine and autocrine neurotrophic factor distributed in the brain and crucial for normal growth, development, and plasticity. Studies suggest that in serum and exosome levels of BDNF decrease in patients with MDD, but increase after clinical improvement and antidepressant treatment [41]. Results from a meta-study further suggest that levels of BDNF in peripheral blood of the patients suffering from MDD increased after the effect of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation and ketamine therapy, which reflects their potential as biomarker for therapy response evaluation [42]. To assess the efficiency of the MDD treatment, proinflammatory or anti-inflammatory markers are generally used in combination to increase the precision. For example, IL-6, IL-1 β , and TNF- α have been used in combination to monitor the efficiency of acupuncture therapy in depressed patients [43]. It is important to note that dietary and lifestyle habits influence the level of MDD biomarkers in patient-derived samples. For example, levels of CRP were found to be higher (5.5 mg/L) in the obese MDD patients compared to the non-obese patients (2.0 mg/L) [44]. Similarly, for patients with smoking habits, the level of CRP was found to be higher (4.7 mg/L) compared to the non-smoking individuals having a healthier lifestyle (0.8 mg/L) [44]. Therefore, dietary and lifestyle factors need to be taken into account while evaluating the response of MDD biomarker for the diagnostics and within therapy response studies.

Micro-RNAs (mi-RNAs) are small endogenous non-coding molecules consisting of 10 to 25 nucleotides responsible for gene-silencing at post-transcriptional levels [45]. Recent developments related to the findings of mi-RNA offer an exciting possibility of their application as biomarkers for MDD, as the blood cells expressing mi-RNAs are studied in monitoring antidepressant response [46]. They play a vital role in regulating various biological mechanisms involving the pathological process of depression such as neurogenesis, neuroplasticity, and the inflammatory response [47]. Various mi-RNAs including mi-RNA-9, mi-RNA-144, and mi-RNA-323a have been directly associated with MDD, as identified through high-throughput RNA sequencing [48-50]. Reports suggest that mi-RNA-134 was significantly downregulated in the plasma of individuals suffering from depression [51]. Clinical studies in human patients and animals verified that mi-RNA-144-3p can successfully predict severity of depression and helps in MDD diagnosis [52]. Similarly, mi-RNA-218-5p was found to be overexpressed in the prefrontal cortex of stressed rats, furthermore it is also related to the social avoidance in adult mice which can be interpreted as symptomatic for depressive behaviour [53]. Another mi-RNA biomarker, mi-RNA-206-3p, was also reported to be elevated in the mouse hippocampus in chronic social defeat stress situations, and involved in depressive behaviour by regulating BDNF synthesis in a negative manner [54]. Additionally, a small number of so-far identified potential exosomal mi-RNAs may also serve the purpose of MDD biomarker. For example, mi-RNA-144-5p, and mi-RNA-16-3p are reported to be associated with mood stabilization and stress response [55,56]. Studies further suggest that the level of mi-RNA-451a is altered in the serum and CSF samples from the MDD patients [57].

Proteases are key enzymes in the human body and can cleave peptides or proteins [58]. These enzymes play a vital role in many biological process including proliferation, differentiation, immunity and apoptosis [58]. Recent studies show their extended application as diagnostic, prognostic, and therapeutic biomarkers for MDD. Particularly, MMPs 2 and 9 have been found as potential biomarkers for MDD. A significant fluctuation in the MMP-2 and MMP-9 levels has been reported in depressed individuals compared to healthy controls [34]. The level of MMP-9 in the depressed individuals was found to be decreased for MDD and schizophrenia patients, however MMP-2 levels increased for MDD but remained unaffected in the schizophrenia patients [59]. These specific changes in the MMP levels

indicate the significance of using a combination of biomarkers for the precise diagnosis of MDD. Amino acids are known to play a vital role in the synthesis of different neurotransmitters like dopamine and serotonin, which are linked to depression [60]. Some studies suggest that imbalances in specific amino acids may be associated with the progression or onset of MDD, and therefore act as potential biomarkers for diagnostic purposes [60] [61]. For example, the level of tryptophan, which is a precursor of serotonin is reported to decrease in the peripheral blood of the patients suffering from MDD [62]. It is often reported that MDD patients have metabolic abnormalities; therefore, biomarkers related to metabolism have attracted significant attention. Recent results reveal that the decreased levels of plasma cholesterol is linked to increased cases of MDD in older men [63]. Further evidences suggest a positive correlation between the increased level of triglycerides and cholesterol with MDD [64]. Other important findings related to metabolic abnormalities suggest that high levels of fat and lipoproteins and low levels of high density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol and apolipoproteins are linked to an increasing number of cases of MDD [65]. Cortisol is primarily known as a stress hormone, and MDD patients showed higher levels of cortisol compared to the control groups [66]. Cortisol is also demonstrated to be the only factor in predicting the onset and recursion of MDD [67]; however, the predictive ability of cortisol may be affected by the disease status of the individual [68]. Melatonin, is another hormone recognized for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, and in MDD patients its level is found to be decreased, which may be linked to the disruption of the melatonin secretion system [69].

In addition to the above-mentioned MDD biomarkers, there are also other significant groups like circular RNA (circRNA) biomarkers. Due to the higher enrichment and stability in synapses, circRNAs are intensively studied for neuropsychiatric diseases diagnostics [70]. Studies suggest that circular RNA DYM (circDYM) inhibits neuroinflammation by targeting miRNA-9 to control the ubiquitination of HSP90 (heat shock protein 90), and is also found to be upregulated in the plasma of patients suffering from MDD [71]. Similarly, the concentration of the plasma circHIPK2 in MDD patients was highly elevated compared to the healthy controls, reflecting its potentials for diagnostic applications [72]. Another class of potential biomarkers include long noncoding RNAs (lncRNA), which were previously considered as non-functional sequences. However, they were recently discovered to play a key role in regulating the neuronal functions and pathophysiology of psychiatric diseases [73]. For example, lncRNA Gm2694, which causes endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress by disrupting the function of Glucose-Regulated Protein 78 (GRP78) has a potential in MDD therapy response monitoring [74]. Neurotransmitters resemble other potential biomarkers associated with MDD, which may be used to distinguish between MDD patients and healthy subjects [75]. The monoamine-based neurotransmitter hypothesis was proposed in the last century, and decreased level of dopamine and the 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) are considered as the primary cause of depression [61]. It was also studied that the reduced 5-HT receptor number and the sensitivity may also reflect the depression level [76]. An imbalance in the inhibitory neurotransmitter gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) and excitatory neurotransmitter glutamate can also be observed in MDD patients [77]. The variation of potential biomarkers in the body fluids, action mechanism and available antidepressants are summarized in the **Table 2**.

Table 2: List of MDD biomarkers, their alteration in body fluids of MDD patients, know mechanism, and related antidepressant therapy.

<i>MDD Biomarker</i>	<i>Variation</i>	<i>Biofluids</i>	<i>Effect/Mechanism</i>	<i>Antidepressant treatment</i>	<i>References</i>
<i>Protease (MMP-9)</i>	Down	Serum; Plasma	Unregulated enzyme activity linked with proliferation, differentiation, immunity, and apoptosis	ECT, Imipramine	[34, 58]

<i>BDNF</i>	Down	Serum; Blood; Exosome	Synaptic plasticity, neurotrophic factors, and normal growth	Ketamine, ECT, TMS	[41,42,78]
<i>Tryptophan</i>	Down	Serum; Plasma; Blood	Vital amino acid, and predecessor of serotonin	Albiflorin	[36,40,79-81]
<i>Melatonin</i>	Down	Serum; Saliva	Disrupted circadian rhythm brings depressive state	N/A	
<i>HDL</i>	Down	Blood	Nonregulated lipid metabolism reduces HDL level	Sertraline; Escitalopram	[43,65,81,82]
<i>CircDYM</i>	Down	Blood; Serum; Exosomes	Microglial activation and neuroinflammation; miR-9/HSP90 ubiquitination	rTMS	[83,84] [84]
<i>Interleukins</i>	Up	Blood; Serum; Plasma	N/A	Venlafaxine; Paroxetine	[40,81]
<i>Cortisol</i>	Up	Saliva, blood, urine	activating metabolism, regulating mental reactions against stress	N/A	[66]
<i>miRNA-144-3p</i>	Up	Blood	Linked to transcription factor TCF7, inflammatory response	Ketamine	[52]
<i>miRNA-9-5p</i>	Up	Serum	Associated with microglial activation and neuroinflammation, Suppressor of signal transduction 2 (SOCS2)	Ketamine; Fluvoxamine	[48,85]
<i>miRNA-146a-5p</i>	Up	Serum; Plasma	Spontaneous discharge cortical atrophy, and neurogenesis	Curcumin; Duloxetine	[86, 87] [87, 88]

ECT: Electroconvulsive therapy; TMS: Transcranial magnetic simulation

Utilization of potential MDD biomarkers for monitoring therapy response depends on their specificity, reliability, and clinical utility. Validation of these MDD biomarkers involves different analytical and clinical validation steps. Analytical validation focuses on characteristics like accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, and inter-laboratory reproducibility [90]. This kind of validation is achieved by evaluating the association between the respective biomarker and disease status, demographic or clinical characteristics (e.g. BMI). Different metrics are also used to monitor differences between specificity, sensitivity and discrimination. For example, area under the curve (AUC) from the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) is an important measure in analyzing the discriminating ability of the biomarkers. The AUC value ranges from 0 to 1 and a higher value reflects the higher discrimination ability of the biomarker. For clinical validation of the biomarkers, studies aim to evaluate the link between the biomarker and endpoint of interest (clinical validity and utility), which is typically accomplished through studies that account for confounders, as well as longitudinal and case-control studies. [90].

Alteration in the MDD biomarker concentration in the body fluids offer a unique opportunity to monitor the therapy response through their detection using biosensors [61]. Depending on the bio recognition elements (antibodies, aptamers, peptides, and MIPs), detection mechanism for the MDD biomarkers

may vary from direct, enzymatic to aptameric [61]. In this regard, graphene is a suitable electrode material, as it has successfully been implemented in designing sensors for several biomarkers including plasma metabolite biomarkers, such as dopamine utilizing different mechanisms. Direct detection mechanisms involve the application of voltammetry techniques like cyclic voltammetry, and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) to capture transient neurotransmitter activity [88]. Enzymatic sensors rely on the electron transfer which arises from the reaction between the immobilized enzyme and the target analyte like dopamine, where the immobilized enzyme like tyrosinase catalyses dopamine to o-dopaquinone which can be electrochemically detected [88]. Aptamer-based detection involves the immobilization of aptamers (short sequences of nucleic acid, 20-100 bp) onto the electrodes. These aptamers show conformational changes upon binding with the target analyte [89].

3. Application of graphene and its derivatives in designing biosensors for MDD in therapy response monitoring: the detection of the abovementioned MDD biomarkers is conventionally performed using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS), enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), rate scattering turbidimetry and other related methods [61]. These techniques offer high accuracy and sensitivity for the detection of biomarkers in body fluids. However, high associated cost and challenges like large equipment sizes, complex measuring steps or long analysis time pose significant challenges in integrating these methods into point-of-care technologies (POCT). Therefore, it is necessary to detect MDD biomarkers with an easy-to-use method that is suitable for multiple scenarios to meet the urgent requirements of healthcare systems. The most common POCT includes electrochemical/electrical biosensors which allow for miniaturization of the devices, fast response times, low-cost, and real time monitoring. As mentioned above, graphene and its derivatives offer several advantages in designing biosensors due to their excellent physicochemical properties and have a potential in designing POCT system for monitoring of MDD biomarkers. Among them, properties like mechanical stability and durability, high electrical conductivity and surface area, chemical versatility and biocompatibility are highly specific for biosensing applications [91]. Here, we highlight the detection of promising MDD biomarkers using graphene-based platforms. A summary of MDD biosensors for therapy response monitoring designed using the graphene related 2D materials have been summarized in **Table 3**. A screen-printed electrode designed using graphene ink was utilized for the label-free monitoring of cortisol in the range of 0.10 to 100 ng/mL [92]. For this, the graphene was modified with aptamers using streptavidin-coated magnetic particles followed by monitoring the specific interaction between cortisol and the aptamer using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). In another report, reduced graphene oxide (rGO) was used as a transducer and for the immobilization of anti-cortisol antibodies [93]. EIS measurements showed the detection of cortisol with a wide detection range of 10 pM–100 nM in human saliva. Additionally, the sensors showed high degrees of selectivity and negligible interference with the cortisol analogs aldosterone, and progesterone. A single layer graphene sheet has been implemented in designing field-effect transistor (FET) biosensors for the cortisol detection in human sweat [94]. The fabricated graphene-based FET biosensors were able to detect up to 0.2 nM concentrations with a detection range between 1 nM -10 μ M cortisol in physiological fluid with higher sensitivity and selectivity [94]. Considering the potential of TNF- α as a MDD biomarker for diagnostics, various graphene-based detection platforms have been reported. For example, an aptamer-modified monolayer graphene FET biosensor offered sensitive detection of TNF- α in human biofluids. In detail, two different methods known as direct and indirect immobilization were studied for the aptamers to evaluate their influence on the carrier mobility of graphene for sensing applications [95]. The direct method based on the immobilization of aptamers with pyrene groups that attach to the graphene via π - π interactions. In the case of indirect approach the attachment relies on 1-pyrenebutanoic acid succinimidyl ester based linkers, which offers detection of TNF- α in sweat with a limit of detection of 10 pg/mL [95]. In other reports, rGO nanocomposite-derived platforms offered a label-free impedimetric detection of TNF- α in human serum [96]. The reaction mechanism relies on the change in resistance due to the movement of a redox probe towards the conducting electrode. The antibody-coated rGO composite showed a sensitive impedimetric detection of 0.78 pg/mL with a linear range of 1-10000 pg/mL [96]. Another rGO nanocomposite was used for label-free amperometric detection of

TNF- α in live cells [97]. For designing the sensor, anti-TNF- α capture antibodies were immobilized on the rGO surface using carbodiimide coupling chemistry, and introduction of TNF- α secreted by live BV-2 cells offered sensitive detection having accuracy comparable to commercial ELISA [97]. An electrochemical device was designed for real-time and in-situ monitoring of IL-6 using the graphene fiber nanocomposite [98]. The sensing fiber was designed using the graphene oxide/carbon nanotube composite immobilized with an IL-6 aptamer (5'-SH-(CH₂)₆-GGT GGC AGG AGGACT ATT TAT TTG CTT TTC T-Ferrocene-3'). The detection mechanism relies on the structural changes of the aptamer undergoing binding induced conformational changes due to the attachment of IL-6 molecules, resulting in larger distance of the probe from the electrode surface, producing a reduced redox signal. Square wave voltammetry (SWV) was applied for the detection of IL-6 in the concentration range of 1 pg/mL to 100 ng/mL. The sensor also offered real-time monitoring of IL-6 in sweat samples in the concentration range of 10 pg/mL to 1 ng/mL [98]. A mono layer graphene FET biosensor was reported for the detection of IL-6 protein using a flexible platform [99]. For the fabrication of the sensor, the graphene surface was modified with a linker followed by the immobilization of aminated (5') probe DNA aptamers. The sensor offered detection of IL-6 in static mode in the concentration range of 10 pM to 100 nM, while real-time continuous monitoring was achieved within the concentration range of 10 pM and 1 nM. In another effort to utilize graphene oxide (GO) as sensing electrode, a nano-sandwich platform for the IL-6 detection was designed. For this, anti-IL-6 detection antibodies were covalently attached to the GO [100]. The sensor demonstrated selective detection of IL-6 over the range of 1–300 pg/mL with the lowest measurable concentration of 1pg/mL.

The detection of CRP is usually performed using the assay (high sensitivity CRP) which can detect the CRP in blood (~0.007mg/L to 3–5mg/L) [39], however the use of graphene based biosensors significantly improves the detection limit of the CRP, which may be helpful in early diagnosis of MDD. In a healthy human, the concentration of CRP ranges from 1-10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. An increase in the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ may indicate a possible inflammation [101]. Therefore, graphene-based biosensing platforms may assist in achieving better sensitivity. For example, biosensors designed on porous GO can detect CRP in the linear range of 0.001–50 ng mL^{-1} [99] [102]. In this report, GO was modified with gold nanoparticles, which act as signal amplifiers and helped to achieve the detection limit of 0.0003 ng/mL . Here, the DNA aptamer-modified GO platform offered a selective and sensitive determination of CRP in human blood using EIS technique. In another report, graphene-based screen-printed electrodes were utilized to design an electrochemical immunosensor for CRP detection in a sandwich-type format [103]. The graphene electrode was modified with two CRP-specific antibodies, an unlabeled capture primary antibody, and an electrochemically detectable anthraquinone-labeled signaling secondary antibody [103]. The CRP concentrations were detected in the range of 0.01–150 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in human serum using DPV technique. Further improvements were made to design a miniaturized smartphone-based POCT device to facilitate the CRP detection using graphene electrodes [104]. In this report, in place of conventional antibodies, nanobodies were immobilized onto the graphene electrode and CRP was detected in the range of 10 ng mL^{-1} –100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with an improved detection limit of 7.6 pg/mL in human serum samples [104].

Graphene-based biosensors have been reported for the detection of various mi-RNA biomarkers including mi-RNA-137. Electrochemically reduced GO nanocomposite modified screen-printed electrodes were utilized for the detection of mi-RNA-137 with a linear range from 5.0 to 750.0 fM with a superior detection limit of 1.7 fM [105]. The designed sensors can distinguish between the target and non-target oligomers offering the desired specificity, and further demonstrated sensing capabilities in human serum relevant for clinical applications. In other reports, a GO nanocomposite was shown to be highly sensitive towards the detection of mi-RNA-137 [106]. Another mi-RNA biomarker, miRNA-34a, was detected using a GO-based platform for impedimetric sensing [107]. For the sensor fabrication, pencil graphite electrodes were modified with GO followed by the immobilization of DNA-RNA hybrids by forming a peptide bond between the carboxylic group of GO and the amino group of the 5'sites of the hybrid. The electrochemical detection of miRNA-34a was performed using different

concentrations in the range of 0-10 µg/mL with a detection limit of 1.9 µg/mL with good selectivity against other mi-RNAs [107].

Electrochemical and electrical biosensors utilizing graphene and its derivatives as transducer material are frequently utilized for the detection of different proteases biomarkers. Depending on the kind of peptide the detection mechanism may be either labelled (modification of peptides with reporter molecules like methylene blue) or label-free (using solution with redox couple, e.g., $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-/4-}$) to monitor the change in the signal. Caspases belong to a family of the cysteine proteases, and Caspase-3 plays a vital role in regulating external and internal apoptosis pathways, it also acts a biomarker for depression [108, 109]. As this protease can cleave and recognize the C-terminus of Asp-Glu-Val-Asp (DEVD), altering the signal due to the change in the thickness of electrical double layer offers an excellent mechanism to design biosensors [110]. For example, a GO-sensing platform was reported for the detection of Caspase-3 activity using an electrochemical measurement technique [111]. For this, the peptide was immobilized on GO through π - π interaction, followed by the measurement of signal which increased on increasing amounts of Caspase-3 with a linear range of 0.5 -2000 pg/mL, with the lower detection limit of 0.2 pg/mL [111]. In another report, a rGO platform was used for the amperometric detection of MMP-2. Sensor fabrication was achieved by the immobilization of a cleavable peptide (NH_2 -Gly-Gly-Lys-Gly-Arg-Val-Gly-Leu-Pro-GlyCys-SH) on the rGO nanocomposite [112]. The introduction of different concentrations of MMP-2 on the sensor surface led to the change in electrochemical signal due to the cleaving of the immobilized peptides. The reported sensor can detect different concentrations of MMP-2 in the range of 0.01-10 ng/mL, demonstrating the potential of novel cleavage-based sensing mechanisms in designing biosensors for MDD biomarkers.

Apart from graphene and its derivatives, other nanostructured materials were also reported for designing biosensors for the detection of MDD biomarkers. For example, carbon nanotube (CNTs, 1D NM) electrodes were utilized to detect salivary cortisol using DPV technique in the detection range from 50 fM to 100 nM [113]. Another key MDD biomarker, IL-6 was detected using label-free CNTs based electronic biosensor [114]. Among the members of 2D NM family, molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) nanosheets were utilized for the detection of various MDD biomarkers. For example, cortisol was detected in human sweat using MoS_2 nanocomposite in the range of 1-500 ng/mL with the detection limit of 1 ng/mL using EIS technique [115]. In another report, nanoflowered structures derived from the MoS_2 nano sheets offered sensitive detection of $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ with a broad linear detection range (1–200 pg/mL) and a limit of detection of 0.20 pg/mL in serum samples [116]. Graphene quantum dots (a member of 0 D NM family) were utilized for the electrochemical detection of cortisol in the detection range of 0.1 pg/mL – 100 ng/mL [117]. Significant development in the field of nanostructured materials since the last two decades offers a unique opportunity to utilize them for designing biosensors for MDD biomarkers. However, considering the development of biosensing technologies for out of laboratory settings, graphene and its derivatives are known as better candidates compared to other types of nanostructured materials. For example, graphene exhibits ballistic electron transport resulting into fast charge transfer compared to CNTs, offers high sensitivity and can enable the detection of extremely low concentrations of the respective MDD biomarkers. Other factors include ease of synthesis, as GO/rGO have more environment-friendly and cost-effective synthesis protocols compared to advanced 2D materials like MXenes. Also in the terms of stability they are superior in aqueous medium in comparison to the MXenes and MoS_2 , which are known to be oxidized in air and aqueous environments [118,119].

Table 3: A summary of biosensors for the detection of MDD biomarkers designed using graphene-based 2D nanomaterials using electrochemical/electrical methods.

MDD Biomarker	Graphene/derivatives	Detection method Electrochemical/FET	Biofluids	LoD	Linear range	References
Cortisol	Graphene ink	EIS	Sweat	2.1 pg/mL	0.10 -100 ng/mL	[92]
	Graphene ink	FET	Saliva	N/A	0.01-10 ⁴ nM	[120]

<i>TNF-α</i>	rGO	EIS	Saliva	10 pM	10 pM–100 nM	[93]
	GO	CV	Sweat	N/A	0.1–150 ng/mL	[121]
	rGO composite	EIS	Serum	0.78 pg/mL	1-1000 pg/ml	[96]
	Monolayer Graphene	FET	Tears	2.75 pM	0-100 nM	[122]
<i>IL-6</i>	rGO composite	SWV	PBS	0.1 pg/mL	0.1-150 pg/ml	[97]
	GO	SWV	Serum	5 pg/mL	5-200 pg/mL	[123]
	Monolayer Graphene	FET	PBS	N/A	10 pM to 100 nM	[99]
	rGO composite	Amperometry	Serum	0.42 pg/mL	0.97 to 250 pg/mL	[124]
<i>CRP</i>	GO	DPV	<i>in-vivo</i>	1 pg/mL	1–300 pg/mL	[100]
	GO	SWV	Serum	5 pg/mL	5-150 pg/mL	[123]
	rGO composite	EIS	Serum	0.08 ng/mL	1-1000 ng/mL	[125]
	Monolayer Graphene	FET	Saliva	39 nM	0-388 nM	[126]
<i>mi-RNA</i>	Graphene ink	DPV	Serum	1.50 ng/mL	0.01 to 150 μ g/mL	[103]
	GO	DPV	Serum	0.29 pg/mL	0.001-100 ng/mL	[127]
	GO	EIS	Serum	1.9 μ g/mL	0- 10 μ g/mL	[107]
	GO composite	Electrical (I-V)	Serum	10 fM	1fM-10 pM	[106]
<i>Protease</i>	rGO composite	DPV	Serum	1.7 fM	5.0 to 750.0 fM	[105]
	GO	DPV	PBS	7.5 μ g/mL	5.0–35.0 μ g/mL	[128]
	rGO composite	SWV	PBS	N/A	0.01- 10 ng/mL	[112]
	GO	CV	PBS	0.2 pg/mL	0.5 -2 ng/mL	[111]

PBS: Phosphate-buffered saline

4. Prospects and challenges: wearable devices are becoming an integral part of modern diagnostic tools [129]. These devices are helpful in collecting various parameters in real-time to evaluate actual depression symptoms. The availability of a reliable wearable device for monitoring the MDD therapy response may offer the possibility of an early and personalized treatment for patients and would be significant for developing appropriate preventive measures for target groups at risk of depression. In this regard, the integration of graphene into a sensing platform enhances the possibility of real-time detection of MDD biomarkers for POCT applications. Growing confidence in POCT and wearable devices may allow the real-time collection of data from the patient's natural environment, previously limited to the clinical setting, which will have a significant impact on evaluating the response to various therapies and medications. For example, a graphene-based smart, wireless contact lens sensor was reported for the detection of cortisol in human tears [130]. In this process, cortisol antibodies were chemically bound to the graphene surface where a soft contact lens was integrated. The interaction with cortisol was converted into an electrical signal by the graphene [130]. This futuristic graphene-based smart lens sensor is wireless, battery-free and requires only a smartphone for signal monitoring. Considering the limitation regarding the reliability of the biomarkers, multiplexed detection of different biomarkers adds more reliability in biosensors for MDD. A combination of different MDD biomarkers can reflect a more reliable specific (patho-) physiological state, compared to a single biomarker. Recent efforts aimed to achieve simultaneous detection of MDD biomarkers using graphene-based sensing platforms [131]. Dopamine, melatonin, and 5-HT were simultaneously detected with high sensitivity and selectivity. The linear detection range was 0.1-70 μ M, 0.1-150 μ M, and 0.1-100 μ M with a detection limit of 0.054 μ M, 0.087 μ M, and 0.071 μ M for dopamine, melatonin, and 5-HT biomarkers respectively

[121] [131]. Similarly, GO-based electrochemical sensors were developed for real-time monitoring of different cytokines VEGF, IFN- γ and TNF- α in human serum and artificial sweat [132]. However, efforts aiming to combine real-time monitoring, and multiplexed detection of MDD biomarkers produces highly relevant large sets of data, which may require artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) tools for sorting and predicting the results. Among major challenges in realization of graphene-based MDD biosensors, is biofouling, which arises due to the presence of other materials in biological fluids [21]. These materials bind with the electrode surface non-specifically and reduce the signal and the sensitivity. This is a major hurdle in commercialization of clinical applications for MDD biomarkers; however, recent success in designing graphene-based antifouling coatings [133] may push towards the availability of POCT for MDD in biological fluids in the near future. Debye screening is another severe problem particularly for the G-FET biosensors. In this case, mobile ions present in the biological sample screen charge from the target molecule, reducing the sensitivity [134]. Under physiological conditions, the Debye screening length is 1 nm or less, while the entire length, for example, of an immunoglobulin molecule (IgG, commonly used antibodies as a receptor biomolecule) is approximately 15 nm. This clearly indicates that the target analytes captured by the IgG using G-FET are beyond the screening length and cannot be detected [134]. However, emergence of advanced bioreceptor molecules like nanobodies, fragment antibodies, and aptamers offers a better prospect in overcoming this issue.

5. Conclusions: Considering the global disease burden, there is an urgent need to expand the access to inexpensive and reliable diagnostics for predicting MDD treatment response, which requires an affordable and proven material such as graphene. Electrochemical and electrical devices based on graphene offer reliable methods for device fabrication alleviating the conventional limitations related to device development. Given the significant advancements in graphene-based biosensors for the detection of various biomarkers, the integration of graphene with potential MDD biomarkers offers a promising prospect for the future. In the last few years, significant efforts were made in utilizing graphene-based platforms for the detection of MDD biomarkers as reflected through the increasing number of scientific publications in the field. However, the detection of these biomarkers in biological fluids is still a challenge due to biofouling, lower sensitivity, and stability. Focused scientific efforts are required to address these challenges, which may result in the realization of effective tools for monitoring the MDD therapy response. These developments have the potential to accelerate and sustainably improve the successful treatment of MDD, addressing the urgent need in the healthcare system for effective treatments for the growing number of patients with MDD.

Acknowledgement: Authors would like to acknowledge the “MUNASET” project funding from the European Union (grant number: 101119473).

Conflict of Interest. There is no conflict of interest to declare.

Statement on data availability: No original data have been used in this article.

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